

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND INCREASE COMPUTER
LITERACY AT YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation : *this in the article information technology development and at a young age computer literacy increase, this about state policies comprehensively illuminated .*

The key words : *information , computer , technology , literacy , knowledge , skill .*

From this three year first Our President by before pushed five initiative today spiritual of our lives inseparable part turning has arrived . Especially young _ generation today his positive effects own life in the example obviously witness __ is happening .

In particular , the third initiative within affairs of the population computer literacy increase , information technology curious boys and girls qualifying specialist level take output , programming products Create ability to form service is doing .

The past time during Information technologies and communications development Ministry by advanced international experience based on all city and districts in the center Digital technology training centers formed was found . Electron tijorat and programming free teaching , information technologies in the field business think on innovative skills formation of “ startup ” projects come true remove on noticeable result achieved .

Our state leader initiative with Information technologies and communications development Ministry and Dubai Future Foundation of the United Arab Emirates by instead The ongoing One Million Programmers project _ youth information technology curiosity in stimulation important strategic step was _ The past year 120 thousand per project more reader cover taken . Of these , 18,000 excess courses successful graduation certificate _ received . In the future this the figure is 300 thousand delivery and young people computer technologies in the direction of free teaching and remote education and lessons online transfer opportunity giving information systems to work unload in the eye caught .

The project within eng a lot scholarship recipients Navoi region (36.6 thousand) , Karakalpakstan Republic (27.6 thousand) and the city of Tashkent (24.5 thousand) right is coming . Sirdaryo (4 , 3 thousand) and Jizzakh (5.9 thousand) regions while , lower steps place received _

This year 's " One Million Programmers " project within graduates weight on high the result shown Karmana District 2 School and Call School No. 39 in the district of Uzbekistan Republic Presidents The gift is a Spark car with was awarded .

Our state leader this from from international IT certification capture entered youth up to 50 percent of the cost which was part of covering give function put . These are

efforts third of the initiative tobora wide quloch spread important importance profession is doing .

Exactly at the time youth and officials in the middle straight away communication to do opportunity “ Youth _ appeal ” e platform on research take is going on. He is young ilm take , professional to be _ word with in other words , in life own replace to find service does .

Sohaga oid scientific research to be continued push , more expand Tashkent information in Tashkent region for the purpose technologies universities branches and all in the region technical schools opens .

The population , especially the youth computer technologies and from the internet effective to use teaching for our country 132 Digital across technology training center activity set off put . This from 240 in the centers more than new the work place was created . Twenty a ming of people more than listener computer literacy , programming basics , robotics , web and mobil applications creation , information technologies in the field innovative entrepreneurship basics directions on training courses finished .

Digital technology training centers computer literacy , digital and IT entrepreneurship basics , “ One Million Programmers ”, Frontend Programming , Backend Programming , Graphics and web design , Android apps create mobile _ robotics , cybersport , SMM, IT Yenglish such as 11 species training courses formed reported . Courses successful graduated to students certificate is given .

In Khorezm new - TechBika training project current was made . From him the goal ming people reader girl information technologies and har kind of areas on wide comprehensive training software through high qualifying specialist reaching to prepare focused .

That's it February 12-13 _ days Khorezm in the province TechBika project on conducted 300 people at the event more than woman took part . From the event then to young people skill lessons passed . For now up to 1 thousand 210 people girl this in the project participation reach desire reported .

Also from February 19 to February 26 Khorezm of the province Urgench , Xonqa , Koshkopir , Shovot , Yangiariq , Bagat , Tuproqqala , Khiva , Hazarasp , Yangibazar , Gurlan districts and Khiva in the city Digital technology training centers propaganda measures become passed _ March 1-9 543 people in the tests conducted woman took part . From the exam successful past 123 people female from 10 March Digital technology training centers computer literacy on read began . That's it on February 26 of the year our state leader presided over of women problems hal to do and them social support issues discussion on the surface conducted video selector at the meeting our country of the population about half women that is , their interest protection make , society in life replace strengthen our state social policy important directions ekani note was found .

Current ITWomen.Uz -2021 project _ _ within of women entrepreneurship and computer literacy oid short term offline and online trainings formed reach in the eye caught . Their first stage up to 35 years which was , “ Iron notebook ”, “ Women notebook ”, “ Youth notebook ” included to women designed . Then two ming of people more than woman mobil application and website Create and computer design activities as well as

offline psychological trainings on practical skills increase possible . Reading successful completed 1 thousand 228 people to the woman certificate and different gifts provided are given .

In our country information technologies market jadal development equally IT professionals the need is growing is increasing . Here it is this demand cover in order to businesses qualified IT personnel with provide for local higher education institutions IT incubation under centers formed being done . Current kunda so centers GV Plexanov named Russia economy University of Tashkent branch , Turin Polytechnic in Tashkent University , Tashkent Finance Institute , Tashkent Inha University , Tashkent State economy University , Tashkent Amity University , Karshi engineering economics institutes , Andijon mechanical engineering institutes , Andijon village farm and agrotechnologies in the institute activity shows .

Of youth information and communication technologies in the field of knowledge and ability increasing IT parks place incomparable _ Their to residents financial , marketing, legal and other consulting services show with together , education also in the direction of large projects instead being increased . From this except technopark _ under the IT academy opened , then series directions on leading experts attractive did without training courses formed etilyapti .

Of youth ICT curiosity height inobatga Tashkent news _ technologies University 2020-2021 study year for digital economy bachelor education direction and eight new master's specialty opened . Ministers Of the Court appropriate decision with this higher education in the institution Uzbek - Belarusian joint faculties formed reached 2020-2021 training year for 500 students acceptance was made . In general , today kunda university and his branches total 15 thousand close student scholarship is taking .

Information and communication technologies in the field of continuity in providing foreign experience deep learning , advanced methods local cadres preparation to the system application reach current is _ Therefore , in 2019 in Tashkent Amity universities activity set off put . Unga foreign 17 PhDs from countries _ has a professor - teacher attractive was made . The past training 498 per year student this of the university first kursini finished . 2020-2021- training year for login exams complete online in the form of formed and so on higher education 384 people to the institution student acceptance was made .

In our capital Inha also studying at the university process intense . Exactly at the time this education There are 51 professors and teachers at the university and assistant activity walking . Of students general soni 1 506 nafar .

Muhammad al- Khwarizmi named information and communication technologies direction oid sciences deepening to teach specialized at school Of Uzbekistan future advanced staff education is getting . Current training in the year their safi more expanded . Acceptance the quota reached 330 marked and login exams in our country first marotaba online in the form of two stage was held .

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